

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

Grant agreement ID: 101091268

Guidelines for Community of Practice (CoP) management at local level

Project	NOVASOIL
Project title	Innovative business models for soil health
Work Package	WP5. Building a Community of Practice and dissemination strategy
Deliverable	5.3
Period covered	36 months
Publication date	28/04/2023
Dissemination level	PU
Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this report	EVENOR
Authors	Blanco-Velázquez Francisco José, Gonzalez-Peñaloza Félix, Bravo-García Javier, Alonso-Martín F Anaya-Romero María
Contributors	All partners

Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	DE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

The document has been shared with the consortium allowing compile inputs and comments. The consortium provided comments about the approach and the selection of national contact point for CoP management.

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	03/04/2023	EVENOR	First draft within approach
2	V1.1	17/04/2023	EVENOR	Draft version circulated by email
3	V1.2	24/04/2023	PARTNERS	Comments received and National Contact Point selected
4	V2.0		EVENOR	New version provided

Table of contents

1	Summary	6
2	Initiation of stakeholder involvement	6
2.1	Information and motivation of stakeholders.....	6
2.2	Possible actions.....	7
2.3	What information should you provide?	7
3	Questionnaire for stakeholders	8
3.1	Stakeholders Interest.....	8
3.1.1	Basic information.....	9
3.1.2	Defining the Stakeholder's Interest.....	9
	What is your role or form of interest?.....	9
3.1.3	Current Stakeholder Engagement.....	10
3.2	Snowball Sample.....	10
3.2.1	Other Stakeholders	10
4	Prompts	11
5.	Approach	11
6.	Acknowledgment	12
7.	Annex 1	13
8.	Annex 2	14

1 Summary

This document is meant to provide partners with suggestions and ideas for how to best start stakeholder involvement and to educate relevant stakeholders about the NOVASOIL project to increase their interest in becoming actively involved in the project and the remaining WPs.

The NOVASOIL project's integrated transdisciplinary approach seeks to initiate a process of knowledge co-production and joint learning among pertinent stakeholders from the local to the (sub-)national level. As a result, in each country, a variety of stakeholders (ranging from land users to civil society groups to local governments to industry and government officials) must be identified who are willing to actively participate in this process. The first section contains a list of ideas for applying the Snowball Sample methodology in the project.

2 Initiation of stakeholder involvement

In the following we focus on the first activity – initiation of stakeholder involvement- which prepares the ground for stakeholder participation along the project implementation, and possibly even beyond.

The activity consists of two steps, which serve the same goal, namely to get relevant stakeholders on board:

- A. Stakeholder analysis: to identify all stakeholders – men and women- that 'somehow' influence what's happening in the case study regarding the business model.
- B. The analysis will be useful for the study site teams in making first contact with stakeholders and obtaining local information.

Information and motivation of stakeholders: to make the NOVASOIL project known among stakeholders and motivate them to participate in the project. This is a remarkable point: to have stakeholders promulgate the knowledge gained in the project and implement the different measures with the objective of sustainable development and improved soil health.

2.1 Information and motivation of stakeholders

Main objectives of the activity:

- **Identification:** To identify possibly relevant stakeholders for the NOVASOIL project (to complement the stakeholder analysis)
- **Information:** To create awareness and inform relevant stakeholders (from the local to the national level and EU level) about the NOVASOIL project, its objectives, and its activities.
- **Motivation:** To motivate relevant stakeholders to actively participate in NOVASOIL and to engage in a process of knowledge sharing and joint learning together with other stakeholders from the local to national level and EU level.

The stakeholder involvement can be initiated in various ways through different actions. There are other possible measures and eventually, each

project partner and case study team will have to decide which actions they consider adequate to motivate stakeholders to engage in the project.

2.2 Possible actions

a) Information events

- Consider carefully which stakeholders—both men and women—farmers, landowners, the government, or other stakeholders may be involved in the business model. The identification procedure will be made easier by the stakeholder analysis.
- You can either plan a special event just for this purpose or use upcoming events to tell prospectively interested stakeholders about the NOVASOIL project.
- Use upcoming meetings, workshops, and other gatherings of relevant parties to let them know about the NOVASOIL initiative.
- Use public events such as community meetings, fairs, conferences, etc. to inform a broader public about the NOVASOIL project.
- If organising a special event to introduce the NOVASOIL project, invite a broad range of stakeholders (e.g. land managers, local / regional authorities, extension services, representatives of NGOs, policy makers, industry, etc.), and pay attention to inviting male and female representatives.

b) Media

- Provide the local/regional media - e.g. newspaper, radio - with information on the NOVASOIL project

c) Newsletters

- Disseminate information on the NOVASOIL project through local/regional newsletters, e.g. newsletters of research institutes, farmer organisations, NGOs, Operational Groups, etc.

d) Flyer

- Create a flyer containing relevant information on the NOVASOIL project, as well as contacts at the national level (in addition to the coordinator)
- Disseminate it to relevant stakeholders, pin it to information boards, etc.

2.3 What information should you provide?

The following list (though not exhaustive) suggests what type of information should be given to potentially interested stakeholders.

a) Basic information

- NOVASOIL- innovative business models for soil health
- EU research project: 3 years duration (01/11/2022 – 31/10/2025)
- 16 participants from 10 countries

b) NOVASOIL objectives

- Develop an operational soil health business case framework supporting the analysis of existing business cases that promote soil health.
 - Analyse existing business models, identify the most promising ones and exemplary develop and upscale selected models for soil health promotion. Design supply chains for an efficient upscaling of the identified and measured business models.
 - Develop a testing network for soil business cases and digital models in a toolbox for incentives. Create a digital hub of knowledge for incentives. Additionally, will be developing tools for the estimation of different soil health business models in the project and a decision support tool for soil health business models.
 - Support the implementation of policy roadmaps towards achieving multi-level sustainable development and ensuring evidence-based and inclusive soil health conservation that is coherent with the main EU policy and transnational strategies
 - Develop and promote the involvement of key actors in a Community of Practice (CoP). This CoP will be built based on previous experiences at the European level and will include a national contact point to avoid the language barrier
 - Develop a dissemination and communication material to increase the expected audience
- c) Your case study (if any)
- The study site description: location, size, etc...
 - The study site team: contacts
 - Your specific objectives
 - Project activities and schedule
- d) Stakeholder involvement
- Transdisciplinary approach of the project: combining scientific and local knowledge to find innovation in business models for soil health.
- e) Stakeholder participation
- Exchange of knowledge and experience between different stakeholders: mutual learning
 - Stakeholder workshops and their objectives
 - Interested stakeholders will be invited to participate actively in the different steps and learning activities

3 Questionnaire for stakeholders

3.1 Stakeholders Interest

A stakeholder is anyone who, can affect or be affected by an action or a decision. They may have different interests and act at different scales and some may be hidden. They might be an individual, a member of an organisation or the organisation itself.

3.1.1 Basic information

Name of stakeholder's organisation: e.g University of Leeds

3.1.2 Defining the Stakeholder's Interest

What is your topic of involvement in the project area?

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Education | <input type="checkbox"/> Water management |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Forestry | <input type="checkbox"/> Land use policy and planning |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental protection | <input type="checkbox"/> Community development |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture | <input type="checkbox"/> Research |

Other:

What is your role or form of interest?

- Land owner Land manager Consumer of produce
- Consumer of other services Provider of information to the public
- Provider of information to farmers/foresters/land owners
- Regulation and enforcement Equipment and/or tool provision
- Providing finance to land managers/owners/workers
- Assistance in gaining access to public funding for land management
- Campaigning Community leaders Safety and/or Security provider
- Product certification body

Other:

What is your sector?

- Government NGO Sector: retail Private Sector: industry
- Private Sector: other Academic Private individual
- Public enterprise Civil society Other

What is your main aim of you regarding land management in the study site?

Are you directly involved in a business model related to the soil?

3.1.3 Current Stakeholder Engagement

Which information channels do you prefer participating in the Community of Practice of NOVASOIL?

Networks (e.g. farmer organisation, regional working group, etc.):

Newsletters (e.g. quarterly newsletter from a public authority, a newsletter of the national association of organic farmers, etc.):

Events (e.g. agricultural fair, workshops of extension service provider, village meeting, etc.):

Online communities (e.g. online discussion fora, websites, social media, etc.):

Clubs, organisations or societies (e.g. Young Farmers Association, Women’s Institute):

Others (please explain):

3.2 Snowball Sample

This section should be completed with a sample of stakeholders to extend the analysis beyond what the researcher already knows. For every identified stakeholder, a separate form should be completed – hopefully facilitating a bit of contact between the researcher and the new stakeholder.

3.2.1 Other Stakeholders

These may be people or organisations that they work with, have contact with, or that they feel influence (or are influenced by) their work in some way. Continue on a separate sheet if necessary. The researcher should help the stakeholder in two ways. Firstly, use the prompt sheet to identify the right word to put in each cell. Secondly, use the categories to classify the stakeholders.

Stakeholder	Topic	Role	Sector	Form number

Chose the most important topic

Education
Forestry
Environmental protection and conservation
Agriculture
Research and Development

Product/commodity exploitation
Water management
Land use policy and planning
Community development
Other, Specify:

Chose the most important role

Land owner
Land manager
Land worker (specify tasks)
Consumer of produce
Consumer of other services (recreation, etc.)
Provider of information to the public
Provider of information to land managers/workers
Regulation and enforcement

Equipment and/or tool provision
Providing finance to land managers/owners/workers
Campaigning
Community leaders
Security provider
Provider of other services
Product certification (e.g. organic, FSC)
Other, Specify

Choose one sector

Government
NGO
Private Sector: retail
Private Sector: industry
Private Sector: other

Academic
Private individual
Public enterprise
Civil Society
Other, Specify

4 Prompts

Are there some topics listed that you haven't already named stakeholders for? If so, are there any stakeholders to add? Or do you feel that there is no-one concerned with those topics that influence your work, or that are affected by your work?

Are there any roles that you haven't already named stakeholders for? If so, are there any stakeholders to add? Or do you feel that there is no-one in these roles that influences your work, or that is affected by your work?

Are there any sectors that you haven't already named stakeholders for? If so, are there any stakeholders to add? Or do you feel that there is no-one in these sectors that influences your work, or that is affected by your work?

5. Approach

The National Contact Point (NCP) will be the responsible of the promotion of knowledge exchange among CoP members. The first activity will be sharing the stakeholder questionnaire to the Multiplier Event participants. The aim of this questionnaire will be to communicate the opportunity to be a CoP

member. The CoP member will participate in specific online/in person meetings about:

- WP1: feedback and comments on framework
- WP2: feedback and reactions on models and Choice Experiments
- WP3: feedback and contributions on ToolBox (requirements and needs)
- WP4: feedback and suggestions on policy innovation labs

Additional information or knowledge may be requested. It will depend on the needs of WPs or tasks leaders.

NCP will be the responsible to communicate dates and venues of the meetings.

6. Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the EU for funding, in the frame of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement GA 101091268. The document reflects only the author's view. The Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

7. Annex 1

COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

APPLICATION FORM

Become an official member of NOVASOIL CoP

If you or your organisation is interested in becoming an official member of the NOVASOIL Community of Practice, please complete and submit this form via email to **info@evenor-tech.com**.

1. Information

Gender: Female Male

Name (Personal or entity name):

Affiliation: Self-Employed NGO CSO/CBO Private business
Philanthropy/Foundation Government Agency Public Organization Other

Affiliation name:

Country:

2. Contact details

Email:

Phone:

3. Why you and/or your organisation seek to be a member of the NOVASOIL Community of Practice:

How we intend to use your information:

The information you provided us above will be used to, 1) contact you regarding the meetings within the CoP, and 2) inform you about the progress of the CoP work through periodic reports.

8. Annex 2

Table of National Contact Point for the CoP management

Country	Partner name	Entity
Bulgaria	Ivan Boevsky	NBU
Denmark	Thomas Lundede	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET
Estonia	Kalvi Tamm	METKI
France	Eriselda Canaj	AREFLH
Deutschland	Fabian Frick	TUM
Italy	Fabio Bartolini	UNIFE
Latvia	Inga Berzina	ZSA
Netherlands	Insa Thiermann	WU
Spain	Francisco José Blanco Velázquez	EVENOR
United Kingdom	Guy Ziv	ULEEDS